

Fauna of Heteroptera (Insecta: Hemiptera) in the Republic of Mordovia (Russia)

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Abstract

The suborder Heteroptera (order Hemiptera) is one of the most interesting groups of Rynchota. It is found in various ecosystems around the world and belongs to predators, parasitous (in particular hematophagous), mycetophagous and herbivorous types. Species with mixed nutrition are common. The study is aimed to describe the fauna and distribution of hemipteran insect species in the Republic of Mordovia (the central part of the European part of Russia). The study was conducted from 2004 to 2022. Specimens were collected using traditional hemipteran insect collecting methods (manual collecting, light trap, entomological net, Malaise trap, Merike plates, window and soil traps). We examined 4895 specimens of Hemiptera. Species diversity of Heteroptera (order Hemiptera) of Republic of Mordovia accounts for 363 species from 34 families. Of these, 15 species (*Campylosteira verna*, *Allorhinocoris flavus*, *Grypocoris sexguttatus*, *Acetropis gimmerthalii*, *Geocoris grylloides*, *Platyplax salviae*, *Emblethis ciliatus*, *Aellopus atratus*, *Rhyparochromus quadratus*, *Parapiesma quadratum*, *Berytinus montivagus*, *Pyrrhocoris marginatus*, *Enoplops scapha*, *Dybowskyia reticulata*, *Ventocoris halophilus*) are listed for the region for the first time. Twenty-three species (*Agramma femorale*, *Adomerus biguttatus*, *Aelia acuminata*, *Carpocoris fuscispinus*, *Coreus marginatus*, *Dolycoris baccarum*, *Eurydema oleracea*, *Gerris lacustris*, *Graphosoma lineatum*, *Kleidocerys resedae*, *Labops sahlbergii*, *Lopus decolor*, *Lygus pratensis*, *Nithecus jacobaeae*, *Palomena prasina*, *Polymerus unifasciatus*, *Prostemma aeneicolle*, *Pyrrhocoris apterus*, *Rhyparochromus pini*, *Stenodema calcarata*, *Cymus glandicolor*, *Eremocoris plebejus*, *Aphanus rolandri*) constitute the main population of the Heteroptera fauna given in the dataset. The species diversity of Heteroptera of the Republic of Mordovia is roughly similar in number of species to that of neighbouring regions.

Keywords: insects, common species, rare species, fauna of regions, comparison of fauna, Central Russia.

Introduction

Currently, the loss of biodiversity on a global scale is beginning to manifest itself to an increasingly significant extent (Gray et al., 2016; Wagner, 2020). To study the biodiversity of the world's faunas of individual insect groups, it is necessary to know regional and local faunas (Dvořák et al., 2023; Dedyukhin, 2023; Vorobjeva, Chertoprud, 2023). Such lists of species will

be the basis for the creation of global databases (Dedyukhin, 2022; Ivanova, Shashkov, 2022; Sandanov et al., 2022). The study of regional and local insect faunas, including hemipterans, seems to be a relevant area of scientific research, especially considering their economic and ecological importance. Many species of Heteroptera are numerous in natural biocenoses (Grozea et al., 2020; Shorenko et al., 2022) some are dangerous pests of agrocenoses (Schaefer, Panizzi, 2000; Sadullaevich et al., 2022). One of the main tasks of modern zoological research is to preserve the gene pool and diversity of animal species, to protect rare and endangered species. A biodiversity inventory is, in essence, a project for the development of biodiversity, while at the same time being a project for its conservation (Janzen, 2003). This is especially relevant now, when many communities are experiencing strong anthropogenic pressure (Trujillo-Arias et al., 2023). In addition, climate change is having a significant impact on invertebrate habitat change (Musolin, 2007; Rabitsch, 2008; Ananyev et al., 2023). And the variety of natural conditions Republic of Mordovia determines the fauna features of the region (Yamashkin, 1998).

Heteroptera, or true bugs, are the most diverse group of insects with incomplete metamorphosis. The suborder Heteroptera has more than 42,000 species, 5,800 genera, and 89 families worldwide (Henry, 2009). The catalog of Hemiptera of the Palaearctic contains about 3000 species for Europe (Aukema, Rieger, 1995, 1996, 1999, 2001, 2006). Heteroptera have sucking mouthparts and feed – depending on the species – as parasites, predators or herbivores on different food sources: from blood or hemolymph to plant sap or the cytoplasm of fungi (Schuh, Slater, 1995; Sadullaevich et al., 2022]. The food preferences of phytophagous Hemiptera have not been well studied (Aleksanov, 2023). Sometimes hemipteran phytophages use extraphytophagous food sources (Adler, Wheeler, 1984). Some phytophagous species of Heteroptera are pests (Heliövaara, 1982; Neymorovets et al., 2007; Tillman et al., 2022). Predatory true bugs such as *Orius laevigatus*, *Macrolophus pygmaeus* and some others are used for biological control of harmful insects (Sanchez, 1997; Hillert, 2002). Heteroptera, unique among insects, colonize almost the entire planet, including the ocean surface and Antarctica (Schuh, Slater, 1995).

This study is aimed to describe the fauna and occurrence of Heteroptera (Hemiptera) in the Republic of Mordovia, based on our recently published dataset in GBIF as Darwin Core Archive (Nikolaeva et al., 2023). This is the first complete description of the Heteroptera fauna of the Republic of Mordovia, located in the center of the European part of Russia.

Material and methods

The Republic of Mordovia is located in the center of the East European Plain between 42°11' and 46°45' east longitude and 53°38' and 55°11' north latitude in the interfluvium of the rivers Moksha and Sura (Figure 1). The region is located mainly in the forest-steppe landscape zone, although, in its northwestern part, there is an array of forests of the southern taiga, and in the south, there

are still some preserved steppe areas. Forests cover more than a third of the republic's area. The main part of open landscapes are agroecosystems. There are many pastures and meadows in the region as open ecosystems. They are mostly located intrazonally (in floodplains of rivers, near reservoirs). The eastern part of Mordovia occupies the northwest of the Volga Upland and the western part of the Oka-Don lowland. In this regard, a variety of habitats is observed in the area of study (Yamashkin, 1998). The variety of landscapes determines the diversity of entomofauna, in which, in addition to the typically nemoral and forest-steppe, taiga and steppe species have been actively detected in recent years (Ruchin et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Study area

Material for this paper was collected during the seasons of 2004–2022 (most intensively since 2008) using the generally accepted entomological methods of field research such as hand collection, light collection, net collection, pitfall traps and barrier traps (Golub et al., 2012). Pitfall traps were set from April to September. The traps were 0.5 L plastic cups containing 200 mL of a 4% formalin solution. We installed 10 traps in various biotopes. The distance between the traps was 2 m (Barber, 1931; Golub et al., 2012). We also conducted a study of the dendrobiont fauna of Heteroptera insects using barrier traps (Nikolaeva et al., 2019; Ruchin et al., 2020). Trap is made of transparent dense plastic and has the following device: two transparent plastic plates (45x30 cm) located perpendicular to each other, under which a cone is attached with a plastic cup (Samkov, Chernyshov, 1983; Økland, 1996). The total surface of the “barrier” is 2.7 m² (Nikolaeva et al., 2019). Material from the collections of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve was also used.

To estimate the abundance of a species, we used a scale that was developed by the second and third authors for Scarabaeoidea (Coleoptera) (Egorov et al., 2023). Thus, a single individual means that single specimens of the species was found in one locality in the region, a rare species means species with a population of 10 or fewer specimens found in 2–5 localities. The common species are true bugs found in 6–10 localities, and the abundant species are Heteroptera, found in at least 50% of the studied localities. The collected material was identified by A.M. Nikolaeva, partly A.B. Ruchin and L.V. Egorov. Identification was carried out according to Kerzhner and others (1964), using additional sources (Golub, 1990; Kanyukova, 2006; Belousova, 2007; Namyatova, Konstantinov, 2009). We checked the distribution of Heteroptera using the catalog (Aukema, Rieger, 1995, 1996, 1999, 2001, 2006). We followed the suggested nomenclature in the work of Schuh and Slater (1995). Each observation includes the following information: location (latitude/longitude), date of observation, observer name and identifier name. The coordinates were determined in situ using a GPS device or using Google Maps (Table 1). The dataset contains 2742 occurrences. A total of 4895 specimens were studied.

Table 1. Description of the data in the dataset

Column label	Column description
eventide	An identifier for the set of information associated with an Event (occurs in one place in one time).
occurrenceID	An identifier for the Occurrence (as opposed to a particular digital record of the occurrence)
basisOfRecord	The specific nature of the data record: HumanObservation
eventDate	The date when material from the trap was collected or the range of dates during which the trap collected material
Kingdom	The full scientific name of the kingdom in which the taxon is classified
Phylum	The full scientific name of the phylum or division in which the taxon is classified
Class	The full scientific name of the class in which the taxon is classified
Order	The full scientific name of the order in which the taxon is classified
taxonRank	The taxonomic rank of the most specific name in the scientificName.
decimalLatitude	The geographic latitude of location in decimal degree
decimalLongitude	The geographic longitude of location in decimal degrees
geodeticDatum	The ellipsoid, geodetic datum, or spatial reference system (SRS) upon which the geographic coordinates given in decimalLatitude and decimalLongitude as based. Here - WGS84.
coordinateUncertaintyInMeters	The horizontal distance (in meters) from the given decimalLatitude and decimalLongitude describing the smallest circle containing the whole of the Location
Country	The name of the country in which the Location occurs. Here - Russia.
countryCode	The standard code for the country in which the Location occurs. Here - RU.
individualCount	The number of individuals represented present at the time of the Occurrence.
Year	The integer day of the month on which the Event occurred.
Month	The ordinal month in which the Event occurred.
Day	The integer day of the month on which the Event occurred
recordedBy	A person or group responsible for recording the original Occurrence.
identifiedBy	A list of names of people, who assigned the Taxon to the subject

Results and Discussion

The dataset contains information about 363 species of Heteroptera from 34 families studied during our research (Table 2). Of these, 17 species (*Campylosteira verna*, *Allorhinocoris flavus*, *Grypocoris sexguttatus*, *Acetropis gimmerthalii*, *Acetropis carinata*, *Acetropis longirostris*, *Geo-*

coris grylloides, *Platyplax salviae*, *Emblethis ciliatus*, *Aellopus atratus*, *Rhyparochromus quadratus*, *Parapiesma quadratum*, *Berytinus montivagus*, *Pyrrhocoris marginatus*, *Enoplops scapha*, *Dybowskyia reticulata*, *Ventocoris halophilus*) are listed for the region for the first time. In addition, Table 2 includes one species (*Codophila varia*) previously noted for the Republic of Mordovia in the literature (Plavilshchikov, 1964), which is confirmed by a single collection specimen. Findings of such species as *Anthemina lunulata* and *Staria lunata* (Timraleev, Susarev, 2008) need to be clarified. Thus, the total fauna of Hemiptera in the Republic of Mordovia currently includes 364 species.

Table 2. Biodiversity of Heteroptera species in the Republic of Mordovia

Taxa	Approximate Estimate of the Number
NEPIDAE Latreille, 1802	
<i>Nepa cinerea</i> Linnaeus, 1758	common specimens
<i>Ranatra linearis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	rare specimens
CORIXIDAE Leach, 1815	
<i>Callicorixa praeusta</i> (Fieber, 1848)	common specimens
<i>Corixa dentipes</i> (Thomson, 1869)	single individual
<i>Hesperocorixa linnaei</i> (Fieber, 1848)	common specimens
<i>Hesperocorixa sahlbergi</i> (Fieber, 1848)	common specimens
<i>Paracorixa concinna</i> (Fieber, 1848)	single individual
<i>Sigara falleni</i> (Fieber, 1848)	common specimens
<i>Sigara limitata</i> (Fieber, 1848)	single individual
<i>Sigara semistriata</i> (Fieber, 1848)	common specimens
NAUCORIDAE Leach, 1815	
<i>Ilyocoris cimicoides</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
NOTONECTIDAE Latreille, 1802	
<i>Notonecta glauca</i> Linnaeus, 1758	common specimens
<i>Notonecta lutea</i> Müller, 1776	single individual
HEBRIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843	
<i>Hebrus pusillus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Hebrus ruficeps</i> Thomson, 1871	rare specimens
HYDROMETRIDAE Billberg, 1820	
<i>Hydrometra gracilentata</i> Horváth, 1899	common specimens
GERRIDAE Leach, 1815	
<i>Aquarius najas</i> (De Geer, 1773)	single individual
<i>Aquarius paludum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Gerris argentatus</i> Schummel, 1832	rare specimens
<i>Gerris lacustris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Gerris lateralis</i> Schummel, 1832	common specimens
<i>Gerris odontogaster</i> (Zetterstedt, 1828)	common specimens
<i>Gerris thoracicus</i> Schummel, 1832	common specimens
<i>Limnopus rufoscutellatus</i> (Latreille, 1807)	common specimens
VELIIDAE Brullé, 1836	
<i>Microvelia reticulata</i> (Burmeister, 1835)	single individual
CERATOCOMBIDAE FIEBER, 1861	
<i>Ceratocombus coleoptratus</i> Zetterstedt, 1819	rare specimens
SALDIDAE Amyot et Serville, 1843	
<i>Chartoscirta cincta</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)	common specimens
<i>Chartoscirta elegantula</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens

<i>Saldula arenicola</i> (Scholtz, 1847)	common specimens
<i>Saldula c-album</i> (Fieber, 1859)	single individual
<i>Saldula opacula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	common specimens
<i>Saldula pallipes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Saldula saltatoria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807	
<i>Coranus subapterus</i> (De Geer, 1773)	rare specimens
<i>Empicoris culiciformis</i> (De Geer, 1773)	single individual
<i>Pygolampis bidentata</i> (Goeze, 1778)	rare specimens
<i>Rhynocoris annulatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
MICROPHYSIDAE Dohrn, 1859	
<i>Loricula exilis</i> (Fallén, 1807)	single individual
NABIDAE A. Costa, 1853	
<i>Alloeorhynchus flavipes</i> (Fieber, 1836)	common specimens
<i>Himacerus apterus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	common specimens
<i>Himacerus boops</i> (Schjødte, 1870)	rare specimens
<i>Himacerus mirmicoides</i> (O. Costa, 1834)	common specimens
<i>Nabis brevis</i> Scholtz, 1847	rare specimens
<i>Nabis ferus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Nabis flavomarginatus</i> Scholtz, 1847	common specimens
<i>Nabis limbatus</i> Dahlbom, 1851	common specimens
<i>Nabis lineatus</i> Dahlbom, 1851	rare specimens
<i>Nabis pseudoferus</i> Remane, 1949	rare specimens
<i>Nabis rugosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Prostemma aeneicolle</i> Stein, 1857	numerous specimens
ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836	
<i>Anthocoris confusus</i> Reuter, 1884	rare specimens
<i>Anthocoris limbatus</i> Fieber, 1836	rare specimens
<i>Anthocoris nemoralis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	rare specimens
<i>Anthocoris nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	common specimens
<i>Lyctocoris campestris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	rare specimens
<i>Orius horvathi</i> (Reuter, 1884)	rare specimens
<i>Orius minutus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Orius niger</i> (Wolff, 1811)	common specimens
<i>Temnostethus gracilis</i> Horváth, 1907	single individual
MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833	
<i>Acetropis carinata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)	common specimens
<i>Acetropis gimmerthalii</i> (Flor, 1860)*	single individual
<i>Acetropis longirostris</i> Puton, 1875	rare specimens
<i>Adelphocoris lineolatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	common specimens
<i>Adelphocoris quadripunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Adelphocoris seticornis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	common specimens
<i>Adelphocoris ticinensis</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1843)	common specimens
<i>Agnocoris rubicundus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	rare specimens
<i>Allorhinocoris flavus</i> J. Sahlberg, 1878*	single individual
<i>Amblytylus nasutus</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	single individual
<i>Apolygus lucorum</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1843)	common specimens
<i>Apolygus spinolae</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1841)	common specimens
<i>Blepharidopterus angulatus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Bothynotus pilosus</i> (Boheman, 1852)	common specimens
<i>Brachyarthrum limitatum</i> Fieber, 1858	single individual
<i>Bryocoris pteridis</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Calocoris roseomaculatus</i> De Geer, 1773	single individual

<i>Campylomma verbasci</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1843)	single individual
<i>Capsodes gothicus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Capsus ater</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Capsus wagneri</i> Remane, 1950	single individual
<i>Charagochilus gyllenhalii</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Chlamydatus pulicarius</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Chlamydatus pullus</i> (Reuter, 1870)	common specimens
<i>Closterotomus biclavatus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	common specimens
<i>Closterotomus fulvomaculatus</i> (De Geer, 1773)	single individual
<i>Compsidolon salicellum</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1841)	single individual
<i>Cyllecoris histrionius</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	single individual
<i>Cyrtorhinus caricis</i> (Fallén, 1807)	single individual
<i>Deraeocoris lutescens</i> (Schilling, 1837)	rare specimens
<i>Deraeocoris olivaceus</i> (Fabricius, 1777)	single individual
<i>Deraeocoris ruber</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Deraeocoris scutellaris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	rare specimens
<i>Deraeocoris ventralis</i> Reuter, 1904	single individual
<i>Dicyphus globulifer</i> (Fallén, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Dryophilocoris flavoquadrimaculatus</i> (De Geer, 1773)	common specimens
<i>Europiella albipennis</i> (Fallén, 1829)	rare specimens
<i>Europiella artemisiae</i> (Becker, 1864)	single individual
<i>Euryopicoris nitidus</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1843)	common specimens
<i>Globiceps flavomaculatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Globiceps fulvicollis</i> Jakovlev, 1877	common specimens
<i>Globiceps salicicola</i> Reuter, 1880	single individual
<i>Grypocoris sexguttatus</i> (Fabricius, 1777) *	single individual
<i>Hallodapus montandoni</i> Reuter, 1895	rare specimens
<i>Halticus apterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Halticus pusillus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	common specimens
<i>Heterocordylus genistae</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	common specimens
<i>Heterocordylus leptocerus</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	common specimens
<i>Hoplomachus thunbergii</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Labops sahlbergii</i> (Fallén, 1829)	numerous specimens
<i>Leptopterna dolabrata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Leptopterna ferrugata</i> (Fallén, 1807)	rare specimens
<i>Liocoris tripustulatus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	common specimens
<i>Lopus decolor</i> (Fallén, 1807)	numerous specimens
<i>Lygus gemellatus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	common specimens
<i>Lygus pratensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Lygus punctatus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	common specimens
<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i> Poppius, 1911	common specimens
<i>Lygus wagneri</i> Remane, 1955	common specimens
<i>Macrotylus herrichi</i> (Reuter, 1873)	rare specimens
<i>Malacocoris chlorizans</i> (Panzer, 1794)	single individual
<i>Megacoelum infusum</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837)	single individual
<i>Megaloceroea recticornis</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	common specimens
<i>Miris striatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	single individual
<i>Monalocoris filicis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Monosynamma bohemanni</i> (Fallén, 1829)	single individual
<i>Myrmecophyes alboornatus</i> (Stal, 1858)	common specimens
<i>Myrmecoris gracilis</i> (R. Sahlberg, 1848)	common specimens
<i>Neolygus contaminatus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Neolygus viridis</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Notostira elongata</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	common specimens

<i>Notostira erratica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Orthocephalus brevis</i> (Panzer, 1798)	single individual
<i>Orthocephalus saltator</i> (Hahn, 1835)	common specimens
<i>Orthocephalus vittipennis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	common specimens
<i>Orthonotus rufifrons</i> (Fallén, 1807)	rare specimens
<i>Orthops basalis</i> (A. Costa, 1853)	common specimens
<i>Orthops campestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Orthops kalmii</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Orthotylus fuscescens</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	single individual
<i>Orthotylus marginalis</i> Reuter, 1883	common specimens
<i>Orthotylus nassatus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	rare specimens
<i>Orthotylus tenellus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	single individual
<i>Pantilius tunicatus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	common specimens
<i>Phoenicocoris obscurellus</i> Fallén, 1829	single individual
<i>Phylus coryli</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	single individual
<i>Phytocoris dimidiatus</i> Kirschbaum, 1856	common specimens
<i>Phytocoris intricatus</i> Flor, 1861	rare specimens
<i>Phytocoris longipennis</i> Flor, 1861	rare specimens
<i>Phytocoris populi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	single individual
<i>Piezocranum simulans</i> Horváth, 1877	single individual
<i>Pilophorus cinnamopterus</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	rare specimens
<i>Pilophorus clavatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	single individual
<i>Pilophorus confusus</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	single individual
<i>Pinalitus rubricatus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	single individual
<i>Pithanus maerkelii</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)	single individual
<i>Placochilus seladonicus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	single individual
<i>Plagiognathus arbustorum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Plagiognathus chrysanthemi</i> (Wolff, 1804)	common specimens
<i>Plagiognathus fulvipennis</i> (Kirschbaum, 1856)	single individual
<i>Polymerus holosericeus</i> Hahn, 1831	rare specimens
<i>Polymerus nigrita</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Polymerus palustris</i> (Reuter, 1907)	rare specimens
<i>Polymerus unifasciatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	numerous specimens
<i>Polymerus vulneratus</i> (Panzer, 1805)	common specimens
<i>Polymerus cognatus</i> (Fieber, 1858)	rare specimens
<i>Psallus betuleti</i> (Fallén, 1826)	rare specimens
<i>Stenodema calcarata</i> (Fallén, 1807)	numerous specimens
<i>Stenodema holsata</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	single individual
<i>Stenodema laevigata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Stenodema virens</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	rare specimens
<i>Stenotus binotatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	rare specimens
<i>Strongylocoris leucocephalus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Strongylocoris steganoides</i> (J. Sahlberg, 1875)	single individual
<i>Systellonotus triguttatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	rare specimens
<i>Trigonotylus caelestialium</i> (Kirkaldy, 1902)	common specimens
<i>Trigonotylus ruficornis</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	common specimens
TINGIDAE Laporte, 1832	
<i>Acalypta carinata</i> (Panzer, 1806)	common specimens
<i>Acalypta marginata</i> (Wolff, 1804)	single individual
<i>Acalypta nigrina</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Acalypta platycheila</i> (Fieber, 1836)	single individual
<i>Agramma femorale</i> (Thompson, 1871)	numerous specimens
<i>Agramma tropidopterum</i> Flor, 1860	rare specimens
<i>Catoplatus fabricii</i> (Stål, 1868)	common specimens

<i>Campylosteira verna</i> (Fallén, 1826)*	single individual
<i>Derephysia foliacea</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Derephysia longispina</i> Golub, 1974	common specimens
<i>Dictyla echii</i> (Schrank, 1782)	common specimens
<i>Dictyla humuli</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Dictyla lupuli</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837)	single individual
<i>Dictyla rotundata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	common specimens
<i>Dictyonota strichnocera</i> Fieber, 1844	common specimens
<i>Kalama tricornis</i> (Schrank, 1801)	rare specimens
<i>Oncochila simplex</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1830)	rare specimens
<i>Physatocheila costata</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	rare specimens
<i>Physatocheila smreczynskii</i> China, 1952	common specimens
<i>Stephanitis oberti</i> (Kolenati, 1856)	rare specimens
<i>Tingis ampliata</i> Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838	common specimens
<i>Tingis cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1746)	rare specimens
<i>Tingis crispata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)	common specimens
<i>Tingis geniculata</i> (Fieber, 1844)	common specimens
<i>Tingis pilosa</i> Hummel, 1825	common specimens
<i>Tingis reticulata</i> Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835	common specimens
ARADIDAE Brullé, 1836	
<i>Aneurus avenius</i> (Dufour, 1833)	common specimens
<i>Aneurus laevis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	single individual
<i>Aradus angularis</i> J. Sahlberg, 1886	common specimens
<i>Aradus aterrimus</i> Fieber, 1864	single individual
<i>Aradus betulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Aradus betulinus</i> Fallén, 1807	single individual
<i>Aradus bimaculatus</i> Reuter, 1872	common specimens
<i>Aradus cinnamomeus</i> Panzer, 1806	common specimens
<i>Aradus corticalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	rare specimens
<i>Aradus crenaticollis</i> R.F. Sahlberg, 1848	single individual
<i>Aradus depressus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Aradus distinctus</i> Fieber, 1860	common specimens
<i>Aradus hieroglyphicus</i> Sahlberg, 1878	single individual
<i>Aradus obtectus</i> Vásárhelyi, 1988	rare specimens
<i>Aradus ribauti</i> Wagner, 1956	single individual
<i>Aradus signaticornis</i> R.F. Sahlberg, 1848	common specimens
<i>Mezira tremulae</i> (Germar, 1822)	common specimens
ACANTHOSOMATIDAE Signoret, 1864	
<i>Acanthosoma haemorrhoidale</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Elasmostethus brevis</i> Lindberg, 1934	rare specimens
<i>Elasmostethus interstinctus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Elasmostethus minor</i> Horváth, 1899	are specimens
<i>Elasmucha ferrugata</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	rare specimens
<i>Elasmucha grisea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
CYDNIDAE Billberg, 1820	
<i>Adomerus biguttatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Cydnus aterrimus</i> (Forster, 1771)	single individual
<i>Legnotus picipes</i> (Fallén, 1807)	rare specimens
<i>Sehirus luctuosus</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1866	common specimens
<i>Sehirus morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	rare specimens
<i>Tritomegas bicolor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	rare specimens
THYREOCORIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843	
<i>Thyreocoris scarabaeoides</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens

PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815	
<i>Aelia acuminata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Aelia klugii</i> Hahn, 1833	rare specimens
<i>Arma custos</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Carpocoris fuscispinus</i> (Boheman, 1851)	numerous specimens
<i>Carpocoris purpureipennis</i> (De Geer, 1773)	common specimens
<i>Chlorochroa pinicola</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)	common specimens
<i>Codophila varia</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	single individual
<i>Dolycoris baccarum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Dybowskyia reticulata</i> (Dallas, 1851) *	single individual
<i>Eurydema dominulus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	common specimens
<i>Eurydema oleracea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Eysarcoris aeneus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	common specimens
<i>Eysarcoris venustissimus</i> (Schrank, 1776)	common specimens
<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Jalla dumosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	single individual
<i>Neottiglossa leporina</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1830)	common specimens
<i>Neottiglossa pusilla</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	common specimens
<i>Palomena prasina</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	numerous specimens
<i>Palomena viridissima</i> (Poda, 1761)	rare specimens
<i>Pentatoma rufipes</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Peribalus strictus vernalis</i> (Wolff, 1804)	common specimens
<i>Picromerus bidens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Piezodorus lituratus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Pinthaeus sanguinipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	rare specimens
<i>Rhacognathus punctatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Rubiconia intermedia</i> (Wolff, 1811)	single individual
<i>Sciocoris cursitans</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	common specimens
<i>Sciocoris distinctus</i> Fieber, 1851	common specimens
<i>Sciocoris macrocephalus</i> Fieber, 1851	rare specimens
<i>Sciocoris umbrinus</i> (Wolff, 1804)	rare specimens
<i>Stagonomus bipunctatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Troilus luridus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	rare specimens
<i>Ventocoris halophilus</i> (Jakovlev, 1874) *	single individual
<i>Zicrona caerulea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
PLATASPIDAE Dallas, 1851	
<i>Coptosoma scutellatum</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	common specimens
SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815	
<i>Eurygaster austriaca</i> (Schrank, 1776)	common specimens
<i>Eurygaster integriceps</i> Puton, 1881	rare specimens
<i>Eurygaster maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Eurygaster testudinaria</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	common specimens
PYRRHOCORIDAE Amyot et Serville, 1843	
<i>Pyrrhocoris apterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Pyrrhocoris marginatus</i> (Kolenati, 1845) *	common specimens
ALYDIDAE Amyot et Serville, 1843	
<i>Alydus calcaratus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
COREIDAE Leach, 1815	
<i>Bathysolen nubilus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Ceraleptus gracilicornis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	common specimens
<i>Ceraleptus lividus</i> Stein, 1858	rare specimens
<i>Coreus marginatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Coriomeris scabricornis</i> (Panzer, 1805)	single individual
<i>Enoplops scapha</i> (Fabricius, 1794) *	rare specimens

<i>Nemocoris fallenii</i> Sahlberg, 1848	rare specimens
<i>Syromastus rhombeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	rare specimens
<i>Ulmicola spinipes</i> (Fallén, 1807)	rare specimens
RHOPALIDAE Amyot and Serville, 1843	
<i>Brachycarenum tigrinus</i> (Schilling, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Chorosoma schillingii</i> (Schilling, 1829)	single individual
<i>Corizus hyoscyami</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Myrmus miriformis</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Rhopalus conspersus</i> (Fieber, 1837)	common specimens
<i>Rhopalus maculatus</i> (Fieber, 1837)	common specimens
<i>Rhopalus parumpunctatus</i> Schilling, 1829	common specimens
<i>Rhopalus subrufus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)	common specimens
<i>Stictopleurus abutilon</i> (Rossi, 1790)	common specimens
<i>Stictopleurus crassicornis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Stictopleurus punctatonervosus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	common specimens
<i>Stictopleurus punctatonervosus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	rare specimens
<i>Stictopleurus unicolor</i> (Jakovlev, 1873)	rare specimens
STENOCEPHALIDAE Dallas, 1852	
<i>Dicranocephalus agilis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	common specimens
<i>Dicranocephalus albipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	single individual
BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851	
<i>Berytinus clavipes</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	common specimens
<i>Berytinus minor</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)	rare specimens
<i>Berytinus montivagus</i> (Meyer-Dür, 1841) *	single individual
<i>Neides tipularius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
BLISSIDAE Stål, 1862	
<i>Dimorphopterus spinolae</i> (Signoret, 1857)	common specimens
<i>Ischnodemus sabuleti</i> (Fallén, 1826)	common specimens
CYMIDAE Baerensprung, 1860	
<i>Cymus aurescens</i> Distant, 1883	common specimens
<i>Cymus claviculus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Cymus glandicolor</i> Hahn, 1833	numerous specimens
<i>Cymus melanocephalus</i> Fieber, 1861	common specimens
GEOCORIDAE Baerensprung, 1860	
<i>Geocoris ater</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	rare specimens
<i>Geocoris dispar</i> (Waga, 1839)	single individual
<i>Geocoris grylloides</i> (Linnaeus, 1761) *	single individual
HETEROGASTRIDAE Stål, 1872	
<i>Platyplax salviae</i> (Schilling, 1829) *	single individual
LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829	
<i>Arocatus roeselii</i> (Schilling, 1829)	single individual
<i>Kleidocerys resedae</i> (Panzer, 1797)	numerous specimens
<i>Lygaeus equestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Nithecus jacobaeae</i> (Schilling, 1829)	numerous specimens
<i>Nysius ericae</i> (Schilling, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Nysius helveticus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)	common specimens
<i>Nysius thymi</i> (Wolff, 1804)	common specimens
<i>Ortholomus punctipennis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)	common specimens
OXYCARENIDAE Stål, 1862	
<i>Oxycarenus modestus</i> (Fallén, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Oxycarenus pallens</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)	single individual
PIESMATIDAE Amyot and Serville, 1843	
<i>Parapiesma quadratum</i> (Fieber, 1844) *	rare specimens
<i>Piesma capitata</i> (Wolff, 1804)	common specimens

<i>Piesma maculata</i> (Laporte, 1833)	common specimens
RHYPAROCHROMIDAE Amyot and Serville, 1843	
<i>Aellopus atratus</i> (Goeze, 1778) *	rare specimens
<i>Aphanus rolandri</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Drymus brunneus</i> (Sahlberg, 1848)	common specimens
<i>Drymus ryeyi</i> Douglas & Scott, 1865	common specimens
<i>Drymus sylvaticus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	common specimens
<i>Emblethis ciliatus</i> Horvath, 1875*	rare specimens
<i>Emblethis verbasci</i> (Fabricius, 1803)	common specimens
<i>Eremocoris abietis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Eremocoris fenestratus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1839)	common specimens
<i>Eremocoris plebejus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	numerous specimens
<i>Eremocoris podagricus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	single individual
<i>Gastrodes grossipes</i> (De Geer, 1773)	rare specimens
<i>Graptopeltus lynceus</i> Fabricius, 1775	common specimens
<i>Ischnocoris angustulus</i> (Boheman, 1852)	single individual
<i>Lampoprax picea</i> (Flor, 1860)	single individual
<i>Ligyrocoris sylvestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens
<i>Megalonotus antennatus</i> (Schilling, 1829)	rare specimens
<i>Megalonotus dilatatus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)	common specimens
<i>Pachybrachius fracticollis</i> (Schilling, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Pachybrachius luridus</i> Hahn, 1826	rare specimens
<i>Panaorus adpersus</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)	common specimens
<i>Peritrechus geniculatus</i> (Hahn, 1833)	common specimens
<i>Pterotmetus staphyliniformis</i> (Schilling, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Raglius alboacuminatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	common specimens
<i>Rhyparochromus pini</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	numerous specimens
<i>Rhyparochromus quadratus</i> (Fabricius, 1798) *	rare specimens
<i>Rhyparochromus vulgaris</i> (Schilling, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Scolopostethus affinis</i> (Schilling, 1829)	rare specimens
<i>Scolopostethus pilosus</i> Reuter, 1874	common specimens
<i>Scolopostethus puberulus</i> Horvath, 1887	rare specimens
<i>Scolopostethus thomsoni</i> Reuter, 1874	common specimens
<i>Sphragisticus nebulosus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	common specimens
<i>Stygnocoris pedestris</i> (Fallén, 1807)	single individual
<i>Stygnocoris rusticus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	rare specimens
<i>Stygnocoris sabulosus</i> (Schilling, 1829)	common specimens
<i>Trapezonotus anorus</i> (Flor, 1860)	common specimens
<i>Trapezonotus arenarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common specimens

*—first record for the Republic of Mordovia.

There are details on the distribution and abundance of a few species that can be classified as low abundance and of limited distribution in the region.

Campylosteira verna inhabits all parts of Western Europe. In Russia, it is known only within the borders of the European part (Aukema, Rieger, 1996). This lace bug lives in mosses on calcareous soils with sparse vegetation (Péricart, 1997). In the Republic of Mordovia, the only habitat was recorded in the southern part of the republic (in the vicinity of the Torbeevo village).

Acetropis gimmerthalii is distributed mainly in the southern regions (Aukema, Rieger, 1999). This insect is rarely found in wet and dry meadows. These bugs occur in open habitats and feed on grasses (Poaceae) (Wachmann et al., 2004). In the Republic of Mordovia, the only habitat was

recorded in a large forest clearing on the territory of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve. It was not recorded in neighboring regions.

Aellopus atratus is distributed in Europe (mostly in the southern part) and Central Asia (Aukema, Rieger, 2001). It inhabits young forest belts, protective plantings near gardens, sandy fallows, mounds, gentle slopes of ravines, clearings and other biotopes with ruderal vegetation. *A. atratus* is polyphytophage, but prefers plants of the borage family (Boraginaceae) (Wagner, 1966; Nikolaeva, 2021). It is rare in regions neighboring the Republic of Mordovia (Nikolaeva, 2021). There were two occurrences in the Republic of Mordovia and both were found in forest biotopes within the territory of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve.

Emblethis ciliatus is extremely rarely observed in Central Russia. The species is typical for the south of the European part of the former USSR (Putchkov, 1974). There was some data about the isolated location of the species in the Ryazan region (Kirichenko, 1951). The seed bug prefers steppe areas. In the Republic of Mordovia, two habitats have been identified in the east of the republic. *E. ciliatus* is highly abundant in the biotope with exposed carbonate rocks (Chamzinka district).

Platyplax salvia inhabits Central and Southern Europe (Aukema, Rieger, 2001). In Central Russia, *P. salvia* is distributed along ravines where the food plant sage (*Salvia* sp.) is found (Nikolaeva, 2021; Evsyunin, 2021). In the Republic of Mordovia, it was only found within the Endova tract (a ravine with steppe vegetation), where a food plant is present.

Geocoris grylloides is a European-Siberian species (Aukema, Rieger, 2001). The species is more common in the forest-steppe zone (Lyckovskaya, 2006; Nikolaeva, 2021). In the Republic of Mordovia, it was once found within the territory of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve.

Enoplops scapha is a local species found on sandy soils. Its food plants are Asteraceae. *E. scapha* is a Palearctic species, which gradually becomes rarer towards the north. It is absent from Northern Europe (Wagner, 1966; Aukema, Rieger, 2006). In the Republic of Mordovia, its habitats are located in oak forests and on steppe hills. Both occurrences were recorded in the east of the Republic of Mordovia. *E. scapha* was recorded in the neighboring Ulyanovsk and Ryazan regions (Nikolaeva, 2021, data of the first author).

Rhyparochromus quadratus is a characteristic species for Southern Europe (Aukema, Rieger, 2006). In Russia, the northernmost find was the Lipetsk region until 2016 (Lyckovskaya, 2006). Currently, the habitats of the species for the Republic of Mordovia and neighboring territories are reliably known. This is a typical steppe species, common in virgin areas, as well as in dry and moderately wet meadows. In the Republic of Mordovia, it was found on the territory of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve and beyond.

Pyrrhocoris marginatus is a species of the Southern part of Europe. In Russia, the Voronezh region was considered the northern border of the species' distribution for a long time (Puchkov, 1963; Aukema, Rieger, 2001). Currently in the Republic of Mordovia, it is recorded in nine different places. Most of them are edges or ravines with limestone or chalk. The species is also found in adjacent territories in the Ryazan region and Chuvashia (Nikolaeva, 2021; Nikolaeva, Egorov, 2023).

Pygolampis bidentata is a species with a wide Palearctic range (Aukema, Rieger, 1996). It is rare throughout its habitat, including the European part of Russia. This species is a predator. *P. bidentata* lives and hunts in dry areas along the banks of rivers and lakes. It has a two-year development cycle. The species is included in the regional Red Data Books of the Republic of Mordovia and Samara Region (Red Data Book, 2005; Rosenberg, Saxonova, 2009).

Dybowskyia reticulata is a rare species throughout most of its range. It is distributed in the forest zone of the Eastern Palearctic (Hemala, Rindoš, 2018; Aukema, Rieger, 2006). In the Republic of Mordovia, it is located on the southwestern border of distribution. The only occurrence was recorded near the village of Kitsaevka, Temnikov district.

Ventocoris halophilus is a species common in the Southeast of the European part of the former USSR (Puchkov, 1961). Information about the ecology and biology of *Ventocoris halophilus* is extremely scarce. The food plants are certain species of the Brassicaceae family (Seidenstücker, 1958; Dursun, Fent, 2013). In the Republic of Mordovia, its only habitat is a forest near the village of Kalysha (territory of the National Park "Smolny"). The species was also recorded in the Samara and Ulyanovsk regions (Dyuzhaeva, 2012, data of the first author).

Figure 2 shows the abundance (in absolute terms) of the most numerous species of Heteroptera. It includes *Agramma femorale*, *Adomerus biguttatus*, *Aelia acuminata*, *Carpocoris fuscispinus*, *Coreus marginatus*, *Dolycoris baccarum*, *Eurydema oleracea*, *Gerris lacustris*, *Graphosoma lineatum*, *Kleidocerys resedae*, *Labops sahlbergii*, *Lopus decolor*, *Lygus pratensis*, *Nithecus jacobaeae*, *Palomena prasina*, *Polymerus unifasciatus*, *Prostemma aeneicolle*, *Pyrrhocoris apterus*, *Rhyparochromus pini*, *Stenodema calcarata*, *Cymus glandicolor*, *Eremocoris plebejus*, *Aphanus rolandri*. These 23 species accounted for 56.3% in number and 23.9% in occurrence of all studied individuals. Most of these species are found throughout the field season.

Figure 2. Species of Heteroptera of the Republic of Mordovia with the highest occurrence and highest numbers represented in the dataset.

In the Hemiptera order, representatives of the suborder Heteroptera are one of the most studied groups. Faunistic data have been published for various regions of European Russia (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of Heteroptera species diversity in some regions of European Russia.

Region	Species Diversity	Data
Republic of Mordovia	364	Our data
Ryazan Region	390	Nikolaeva, 2021, data of the first author
Chuvash Republic	319	Kanyukova et al., 2021; Egorov, et al., 2022; Nikolaeva, Egorov, 2023
Saratov Region	195	Grebennikov, Anikin, 2020
Penza Region	200	Zinovyeva, Polumordvinov, 2017, 2023; Shveenkova, Stoyko, 2022
Lipetsk Region	298	Golub, 1996; Golub, Parfenova, 2000; Lychkovskaya, 2006
Voronezh region	380	Golub, Parfenova, 2000; Negrobov, 2005; Kondratyeva, Golub, 2009; Svyatoduh, Golub, 2015
Tula region	290	Evsyunin, 2021
Samara region	549	Dyuzhaeva, 1999, 2012
Bryansk region	151	Data of the first author

The species diversity of Heteroptera of the Republic of Mordovia is roughly similar in number of species to that of the neighboring regions. At the same time, in some more southern regions of the European Russia (Samara region), the number of Heteroptera species is much higher (Table 3). The Tula, Voronezh, Lipetsk, Ryazan and Samara regions were the most studied. These are

the regions where specialists carried out a long-term, targeted research on this group of insects. There were the most species found in the Samara region. This is due not only to a good study of this territory, but also to the fact that the region is located further south than others. True bugs are a group of mostly heat-loving insects, so the number of species increases to the south.

Conclusion

A long-term study of the Heteroptera biodiversity of the Republic of Mordovia has been conducted. We examined 4,895 specimens. It is shown that the species diversity of Heteroptera is 363 species from 34 families. Of these, 15 species are mentioned for the first time in this report. The main part of the fauna consists of 23 species that live in terrestrial biotopes. We have made a comparison of the Heteroptera fauna of the Republic of Mordovia and the nearest regions of European Russia. It is shown that the biodiversity of this group is similar in different regions and largely depends on the degree of study of the region.

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